

THE COMPACTION SPECIFICATIONS FOR HIGHWAYS FILL: PLACEMENT MOISTURE CONTENT RANGE FIXATION

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SUMMARY

Invariably most highways specifications call for placement moisture content of engineered fills and pavement layers geomaterial to be in the range of $OMC \pm 2\%$. Some awarding agencies specify the placement moisture content in terms of percentage of OMC, typically between 75-120% of OMC. These specifications do not consider the moisture sensitivity of some soils, particularly fine-grained soils. A slight increase or decrease in moulding/placement moisture content of the geomaterial can result in a significant loss of strength. This paper examines the compaction and strength of eight soils of different geological formations at a moisture content of $OMC \pm 2\%$ using CBR to measure the bearing capacity of the soil. Shortcomings of specifications based on an arbitrary placement moisture content specification of $OMC \pm 2\%$ are illustrated.

INTRODUCTION

It is known to every pavement engineer that compaction is one of the most critical parameters that improve the soil bearing capacity, subsequently improving the pavement's structural capacity. In most cases, the highway specifications call for the moisture compaction range as percentages of optimum moisture content typically within the range of 75-120% of OMC or as a range of moisture deviation from the optimum moisture content normally within the range of $OMC \pm 2\%$ regardless of the nature of the geomaterials.

There is a huge difference in the bearing capacity of geo-materials at this normally specified moisture compaction range, as demonstrated in this study. For the geo-materials tested during this study, it was established that some geo-materials might

yield very satisfactory results at optimum moisture content. However, when tested at a specified moisture compaction range of $OMC \pm 2\%$, a drastic decrease in CBR was observed.

This paper presents the analysis of the CBR data from eight different geomaterials tested across the usually specified range of moisture content of $OMC \pm 2\%$, statically compacted to 95% and 100% of maximum dry density (AASHTO T180). The range of $OMC \pm 2\%$ has been chosen as the baseline for this study since many specifying agencies widely use it.

THE CBR TEST

The essential features of the CBR test apparatus are fully described in BS 1377: Part 4:1990 [1], AASHTO T193 [2] and CML 1.11 [3]. In CML 1.11, it is prescribed that the geomaterial should be moulded at the optimum moisture content ($OMC \pm 0.3\%$). The CBR can be tested in an unsoaked state at optimum moisture content or four days soaked, depending on the climatic condition of the region as given in the Tanzania Pavement and Materials Design Manual [1999][4]. The CBR is tested at optimum moisture content in the un-soaked state in dry climatic conditions. In contrast, the CBR is tested after four days in soaked conditions in moderate and wet climatic conditions. In AASHTO T193-93 and BS 1377-Part 4-1990, the effect of moulding moisture content on soil strength, particularly for fine-grained soil, is addressed. Paragraphs 3.2 and 3.3 of the AASHTO T193-93 and BS 1377-Part, 4-1990 Paragraph 7.2.1.2 recommend investigating the effect of moulding water content during CBR testing.

"AASHTO T193-93-Paragraph - 3.2: For applications where the effect of compaction water content on CBR is small, such as

cohesion-less, coarse-grained material, or where an allowance is made for the effect of differing compaction water contents in the design procedure, the CBR may be determined at the optimum moisture content of a specified compaction effort. The dry unit weight specified is normally the minimum per cent compaction allowed by the using agency's field compaction specification."

"AASHTO T193-99-Paragraph -3.3: For applications where the effect of compaction water content on CBR is unknown or where it is desired to account for its effect, the CBR is determined for a range of moisture content, usually the range of water content permitted for field compaction by using agency's field compaction specification."

BS 1377 Part 4-1990-Paragraph 7.2.1.2: "...The moisture content of the soil shall be chosen to represent the design conditions for which the test results are required. Alternatively, where a range of moisture content is to be investigated, water shall be added or removed from the natural soil after disaggregation."

Clauses are incorporated into both AASHTO T193-99 and BS 1377 standards to address the effect of moulding moisture content on the strength of the geomaterials. In most cases, this procedure of investigating the effect of moisture content on the strength of the geomaterial is not adhered to by many specifying agencies, consultants and contractors. Thus, it is customary to mould the geo-material CBR specimen at optimum moisture content only and carry out the CBR test after four days of soaking.

FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS OF SOIL COMPACTION

RR Proctor[5,6,7,8] introduced modern procedures for the placement and compaction of fill in four articles published in Engineering News-Record in 1933. Essentially Proctor was concerned to develop an improved method for the control of earthworks by simple laboratory and field tests. He referred his readers to a paper published in Engineering News-Record by Terzhagi (1925)[9] for more specialised soil mechanics knowledge. Proctor's work was

associated with the construction of earth-fill dams and concluded that:

"... it is possible to compact the soil, so firm and hard as to appear entirely suitable for a dam and this same soil to become very soft and unstable when percolating water saturates it".

AASHTO T99 describes compaction test procedures using a 2.5 kg rammer with an energy input of 594 kJ/m³, while AASHTO T180 describes the test procedure using a 4.5 kg rammer with an energy input of 2695 kJ/m³. The Optimum moisture content is defined as the moisture content at which the maximum dry density is achieved using specified energy. Therefore, when quoting the optimum moisture content value of the geomaterial, the applied compaction energy must be stated.

The basic laboratory testing carried by Proctor demonstrated some fundamental features of the compaction of clay soil.

- The density to which a particular compactive effort will bring a clay fill depends on the moisture content of the fill.
- For a given compactive effort, a maximum dry density is achieved at the optimum moisture content. The expressions "maximum dry densities" and "optimum moisture content" refer to a specified compaction procedure and can be misleading if taken out of the context of the procedures.
- At a moisture content dry of optimum, the specified compaction procedure will result in a fill-geomaterial with large air voids, which allows the geomaterial to imbibe a substantial amount of water to saturation resulting in a large fraction of the initial strength to be lost.
- At moisture content significantly wet of optimum moisture content, the specified compaction procedure will produce a fill-geomaterial with minimum air voids and more stable in the presence of water but less stable to resist the load.

These fundamental factors demonstrate that the control of placement moisture content is crucial for field control of compaction.

PLACEMENT MOISTURE CONTENT SPECIFICATION

In most cases, the placement moisture content is specified as either a percentage of optimum moisture content or 2% above or below the optimum moisture content ($OMC \pm 2\%$). The arbitrary choice of this placement moisture content irrespective of the soil type seems practically reasonable because it is impossible to bring the fill material to optimum moisture content all the time. However, the specifying agencies seem reluctant to specify anything different from customary, forgetting that soil types, particularly the nature of the fine within the soil matrix, may influence these requirements. For instance, paragraph 3606(c) of Standard specification for road works 2000 of the Ministry of Works (Tanzania)[10] calls for the fill geomaterial to be compacted at 75% of OMC. No allowance is made for the compaction on the wet side of the optimum moisture content. The geomaterial compacted on the dry leg of the optimum moisture content results in compacted soil full of interconnected air void, which allows the soil to imbibe a large amount of water when saturated. The expansivity potential and permeability of the geomaterial also increase. Thus, specifying compaction on the dry side of the optimum moisture content can be detrimental when compacting some fine-grained and expansive soils.

The specifier always contends that placement moisture content of $OMC \pm 2\%$ or within the range 75%-120% of the OMC will guarantee at least 95% compaction for most soils. With this notion in mind, the designer/specifier will be satisfied that the soil will perform satisfactorily; thus, no effort is made to study the effect of moulding/placement moisture on the strength of the soil and its impact on performance once saturated.

LABORATORY TESTING

Eight soil samples from two different geological locations in Tanzania were used during this study. Three soil samples were taken along Dar-Bagamoyo Road, and five soil samples were taken during alignment sampling of Matomondo – Mlale road in the Iringa region. Specifically, the geomaterial

ranged from Sandy gravel, Silty Sand and Silty Clay.

Results of Laboratory Tests

The soil behaviour at a moisture content of $OMC \pm 2\%$ was investigated by compacting soil samples using modified Proctor compaction test AASHTO T180 to establish maximum dry density and optimum moisture content.

For CBR testing, the soil was statically compacted in a CBR mould at diverse moisture content to achieve the desired compaction effort of 95% and 100%. After that, the compacted CBR samples were soaked for four days. After testing the CBR, the geomaterial was classified using CBR values following the Tanzania Pavement and Materials Design Manual; the CBR ranges are shown in the brackets, i.e. unsuitable ($CBR < 3$), G3(3-7), G7(7-15), G15(15-25), G25(25-45), G45(45-60), G60(60-80) and G80(80+). The geomaterial moisture sensitivity was evaluated by computing the derivative of the moisture-CBR curve. The average moisture-sensitivity measures the rate of change of CBR due to an increase or decrease in moisture content by 1%. The laboratory CBR specimen moulding moisture content is synonymous with field placement moisture content. Therefore the CBR specimen moulding moisture content simulates the field placement moisture content. The summary of test results is shown in Figure 1 to Figure 8.

Figure 1(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

Figure 1(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

Figure 2(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

Figure 1(c): placement moisture content that meets the CBR requirements for various layers

Figure 1: Sandy silty geomaterial (PI=15)

Figure 2(c): Placement moisture content for the geomaterial based on the achieved CBR values at diverse moisture content

Figure 2: Gravel sandy silty (PI =13)

Figure 2(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

3(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

3(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

3(c): Placement moisture content for the geomaterial based on the achieved CBR values at diverse moisture content

Figure 3: coarse sand silty (PI=11)

4(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

4(c): Placement moisture content for the geomaterial based on the achieved CBR values at diverse moisture content

Figure 4: Sandy silt (31% passing 0.075 mm sieve, PI=12)

4(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

5(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

5(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

5(c): Placement moisture content for the geomaterial based on the achieved CBR values at diverse moisture content

Figure 5: 37% passing 0.075 mm sieve size, plasticity index =17

6(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

6(c): Placement moisture content for the geomaterial based on the achieved CBR values at diverse moisture content

Figure 6: 20 passing 0.075 mm sieve size (NP=0)

6(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

7(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

7(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

7(c): Placement moisture content for the geomaterial based on the achieved CBR values at diverse moisture content

Figure 7: 40% passing 0.075 mm sieve (PI=NP)

8(b): CBR values at 95% and 100% compaction at diverse moisture content

8(c): Placement moisture content for the geomaterial based on the achieved CBR values at diverse moisture content

Figure 8: 60% passing 0.075 mm sieve (PI=24)

8(a): Iso-CBR values at diverse compaction and moisture content

DISCUSSION OF TEST RESULTS

Figure 1-8 gives a relationship between moulding moisture content and CBR. Depending on the moulding moisture content and the applied compaction energy, it can be seen that the same geomaterial can be classified as unsuitable (CBR of less than 3), G3, G7, G15, G25, G60 or even G80. This suggests that the CBR value is not an intrinsic property of the geomaterial.

The CBR values of the geomaterial increased as the moulding moisture content increased to a maximum CBR value. Thereafter, the CBR value decreased as the moisture content increased. The maximum CBR value was recorded within the moisture range of OMC±2% at both 95% and 100% compaction levels except for one sample,

which exhibited a maximum CBR value at OMC+2.3% (Figure 3) on the wet-side of optimum moisture content at 95% compaction level. Generally, the CBR-optimum moisture content was within the moisture range of OMC \pm 1%. The summary of the moisture content at which the maximum CBR values were recorded at 95% and 100% compaction levels is shown in Table 1. Thus, there is an optimum moulding moisture content for every geomaterial at which the maximum CBR value is attained. This CBR-optimum moisture content does not necessarily coincide with the optimum moisture content established during the determination of the maximum dry density.

The maximum CBR values for the geomaterial tested ranged from 32-137 and 14-76 when compacted to 100% and 95% of AASHTO T180, respectively. An increase in compaction energy from 95% to 100% of MDD on the dry side of the optimum moisture content significantly increased the CBR values. The relationship between CBR and moisture content at 95% and 100% compaction levels exhibited a well-defined peak for all tested soil samples. The maximum CBR value at 95% and 100% compaction is the peak CBR value which can only be achieved at a particular CBR-optimum moisture content. Thus, if the maximum CBR is recorded at MDD-optimum-moisture-content can only be achieved when the geomaterial is compacted at the moisture content of OMC \pm 0%. If the geomaterial is compacted on either side of the CBR-optimum-moisture content, a drastic drop in CBR value is experienced. On the wet side of the optimum moisture content, an increase in compaction energy is not associated with an increase in CBR values due to over-compaction. It is hypothesised that over-compaction of soil destructs the soil structure by transforming its particle from flocculated structure to dispersed structure. The geomaterial may exhibit over-compaction behaviour when compacted at 100% at a moisture content of more than OMC+1% (Figures 3 and 4).

The moisture sensitivity of the geomaterial was evaluated by computing the average derivative of the moisture-CBR curves. The derivative of the moisture-CBR curve shows the rate of change of CBR with the change in

moisture content. It was observed that the moisture sensitivity increased as the CBR and compaction energy increased. The summary of the moisture sensitivity of the tested geomaterial is shown in Table 2. The iso-CBR contour and derivative plots indicate that the CBR of the geomaterial is sensitive to variation in moisture content on both sides of optimum moisture content. The geomaterials shown in Figures 4 and 6 are extremely sensitive to moisture variation, as evidenced by closely spaced contours. The CBR-moisture sensitivity for soil 4 and 6 was 52.9 and 43.8, respectively, at a 100% compaction level. Thus, a one per cent variation of moulding moisture content is associated with either decrease or increase in soaked CBR of 52.9 for soil shown in Figure 4 or 43.6 for the soil shown in Figure 6. Therefore, a geomaterial with a high CBR value of 100 can be egregiously transformed to zero CBR value geomaterial due to variation of placement/moulding moisture content by 2% (Figures 4 and 6).

Table 1: Moisture content at maximum CBR values

Sample No.	95%	100%
1	OMC+0.9%	OMC
2	OMC-1.0%	OMC-0.3%
3	OMC+2.3%	OMC
4	OMC	OMC-1.1%
5	OMC+0.2%	OMC
6	OMC-0.6%	OMC-1.0
7	OMC+0.8%	OMC-0.8%
8	OMC-1.0%	OMC-0.8%

Table 2: Sensitivity of the geomaterial

Sample No.	Sensitivity at 95% compaction	Sensitivity at 100% compaction
1	3.8	13.6
2	5	16
3	3.3	5
4	10	52.9
5	5.9	18
6	25.2	43.8
7	6.1	15.3
8	19.9	30.6

The pavement design in most countries is based on the CBR values of the geomaterial. During construction, in most cases, the in-situ CBR is not determined. The field density control, even though it measures the

achieved dry density of the geomaterial, usually it is assumed that once the specified dry density is achieved, the specified CBR value is automatically attained. In most cases, the control of the placement moisture content is not given importance while placing the subgrade and pavement layers. This study indicates that achieving the specified dry density does not guarantee that the specified minimum CBR value of the geomaterial has been achieved. Depending on the moulding moisture content, the soaked CBR of the geomaterial compacted to the same dry density can vary from zero to more than 100 (Figure 6). Therefore, the soaked CBR value of the geomaterial is primarily controlled by the placement-moisture content.

The moulding moisture content analysis indicates that the geomaterial may achieve a maximum laboratory CBR value at optimum moisture content or near optimum moisture content. However, based on the test results of this study, the CBR of the geomaterial moulded in the laboratory at optimum moisture content and soaked for four days may not reflect the saturated in-situ CBR value. After saturation, the in-situ CBR value may significantly be lower than the one determined in the laboratory due to variation in placement moisture content. The variation in placement moisture content cannot be regarded as an issue in a dry region owing to the fact that the pavement, in most cases, is operating in an unsaturated state; in the wet region where the geomaterial is likely to operate in a saturated state, the low field CBR value after geomaterial saturation may lead to premature pavement failure. The saturation of the geomaterial and reduction in the CBR value is also an issue of concern where a granular subbase underlies the crushed base. Compaction of the crushed base requires a copious amount of water, commonly termed 'slushing'. The water used during the 'slushing' process may saturate the underlying granular subbase leading to a drastic decrease of the geomaterial CBR value, ultimately leading to premature pavement failure. Pavement failure due to the imbibition of water from the compaction process of the crushed base has been reported[11].

The test results presented herein suggest that the moulding/placement moisture content influences the resultant CBR values and is a critical parameter that governs the resulting CBR value of the geomaterial. Controlling the placement moisture content and the dry density of the geomaterial is vital.

PROPOSED SOIL COMPACTION AND MOISTURE CONTROL

The soil structure and the engineering properties of the geomaterial depend on applied compaction effort and the moulding water content. In most cases, during fill operations, the emphasis during the quality control is placed on achieving the specified dry density and not on the desired engineering properties of the geomaterial. Therefore, what matters most in the field is the achieved dry density; how the dry density is achieved does not matter and is not an issue of concern. Inescapably, the single desired property in the pavement to be achieved during compaction is the minimum CBR value assumed during pavement design. Achieving the desired dry density does not necessarily guarantee that the desired engineering properties of the soil are achieved. Therefore, the project specification for compaction of the fill geomaterial needs to address the need to achieve the minimum CBR value assumed during the design of the pavement structure. The CBR is primarily controlled by the moulding/placement moisture content and the applied compaction effort. Therefore, the project specifications must address not only the minimum required dry density but also the placement moisture content. The placement moisture content of the material depends on the geological formation of the soil, the amount and nature of the fine and the applied compaction energy. The placement moisture content for the geomaterial, particularly for the fine-grained geomaterial, can not be specified globally as $OMC \pm 2\%$ since it is a unique value for every geomaterial at specified compaction energy. This implies that, for the desired engineering properties to be achieved, the placement-moisture content must be established through laboratory testing of the geomaterial's CBR. Based on the laboratory achieved CBR values at diverse

moisture content, the placement moisture content specification can be developed.

It is proposed that the placement moisture content of the geomaterial shall be established through laboratory testing of the CBR value of the geomaterial at specified compaction energy. The placement moisture content of the borrow-area or particular uniform section of fill along the alignment must be established through CBR testing of the geomaterial within the moisture range of OMC-3% to OMC+2%. The moisture content range that yields the desired minimum CBR value at the specified compaction energy for each class of geomaterial shall be the placement moisture content specification for the geomaterial. Thus, the same borrow area may have more than one placement moisture content specification depending on the specified CBR of the geomaterial, i.e. the geomaterial shown in Figure 6, compacted to 95% of the MDD, the placement moisture content for G60 is OMC-1.4 to OMC+0.1%, for the G45 geomaterial is OMC-1.7 to OMC+0.5% and for the G25 geomaterial is OMC-2.3% to OMC+1.1%. The summary of the placement moisture content for various material classifications for the tested geomaterial is shown in Figures 1(c) to 8(c). Testing the geomaterial for CBR through a diverse moisture content range may allow relaxation or more strict control of placement moisture content in the field. It is of considerable advantage to test the soil across the typically recommended or specified moisture and compaction ranges to ascertain the critical behaviour of the soil before approval of any proposed borrow area.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the test results presented in this study, the main conclusions are:

- The CBR of the fine-grained geomaterial value is significantly influenced by the moulding(placement) moisture content of the geomaterial and not the achieved degree of compaction. The CBR value is highly dependent on the structure of the soil formed (dispersed or flocculated) at moulding/placement moisture content and the applied compaction energy. This implies that the same soil compacted at diverse moisture contents to the same dry density produces different soil structures, although mineralogical composition, plasticity and soil texture are the same. Therefore, the critical performance indicator of the geomaterial, such as CBR, and swell potential, will not be the same simply because the dry density is the same.
- A departure of moulding/placement moisture content from optimum moisture content may result in a drastic drop in soaked CBR to zero within the typically specified moisture range of OMC±2%. Therefore, the geomaterial's stiffness and performance are controlled by the placement moisture and not by the achieved dry density, implying that pavement layers must be compacted to the desired minimum density at proper placement moisture content.
- In most cases, the CBR determined at OMC is likely to be the peak CBR value, which can only be attained within a very narrow range of placement/moulding moisture content. Therefore, determining the soaked CBR value moulded at optimum moisture content may not be appropriate for some moisture sensitive geomaterials. The CBR testing at optimum moisture content is not providing a good prediction of the performance of the geomaterial after saturation.
- In most cases, the moisture control during compaction is not given the required importance. The main acceptance field criterion is the achieved degree of compaction. This study indicates that the placement moisture content is a critical criterion to be controlled during the placement of earthworks and pavement layers since it controls the resultant stiffness and the CBR value of the geomaterial.
- The soil test results reported during this study indicate that the CBR of the fine-grained geomaterial is highly variable depending on the placement moisture content and the applied compaction energy. Therefore, the CBR is not an

intrinsic or characteristic property of the geomaterial. The same geomaterial can be classified into several groups of soils suitable for earthworks, improved subgrade and subbase simply by varying the moulding moisture content and the compaction energy.

- The arbitrary placement-moisture content of $OMC \pm 2\%$ specifications is inappropriate when applied to some moisture sensitive geomaterial and can lead to pavement failure if the moisture sensitivity of the geomaterial is not evaluated and quantified. For some geomaterials, a 2% increase or decrease in moulding/placement moisture content can catastrophically reduce the CBR value of the geomaterial to zero.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is proposed to revise the CBR testing procedures given in the CML 1.10 and 1.11 to include a new clause explicitly to address and require investigation on the effect of moulding/placement moisture content on the strength of the geomaterial.

Article 3606(c) of Standard Specification for Road Works 2000 calls for the geomaterial to be compacted at 75% of optimum moisture content, implying that compaction on the wet side of optimum moisture content is not allowed. Some soils are likely to show considerable instability when compacted at moisture content below optimum. Therefore, this clause needs to be revisited to address the effect of moulding/placement moisture content of the geomaterial and to allow the compaction of the geomaterial on the wet side of the optimum moisture content.

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